

COMMUNICATION PLAN

07/04/2021

Define goals of communication
Inform local community about citizen science activities; Grow partnerships in citizen science with partners and externally; Promote Keepers of the sea model of citizen science to inspire public participation in science; Raise awareness on policy-makers about the relevance of citizen-science for data collection on water quality; To strengthen the collaboration between researchers and fishing community.

Map stakeholders / target groups and order them by relevance
Stakeholders: Fishing community, other NGOs, tourism actors, policy-makers and managers, recreational users (e.g. foragers), researchers, aquaculture (e.g. oyster farming), agriculture and industrial agents, general public. Target audience I: Fishing community Target audience II: Policy-makers and managers Target audience III: Researchers

Choose tools to reach them				
	Target audience 1	Target audience 2	Target audience 3	Others
Facebook	Fishing community: posts	Policy-makers and managers	Researchers	general public (30-70 yrs); recreational users, tourism actors, other NGOs
Instagram	Fishing community: posts; stories	n.a.	n.a.	general public (18-50 yrs); other NGOs
Linkedin	n.a.	n.a.	Researchers	Other NGOs, industries
Printed material WQ community guide	Fishing community	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.
Workshop online	n.a.	Policy-makers and managers	Researchers	Other NGOs, industries,

				aquaculture, tourism actors
Website page:	n.a.	Policy-makers and managers	Researchers	general public, other NGOs, industries, aquaculture, tourism actors
Layman's report	Fishing community	n.a.	n.a.	general public, recreational users, tourism actors, aquaculture, industries
Datasets	n.a.	Policy-makers and managers	Researchers	n.a.
Video	Fishing community	Policy-makers and managers	Researchers	All, through website and social media

Schedule activities

March – (22) Launch of the project on social media – Post 1
 April – post 2; Earth day (22)
 May – post 3; website page is launched
 June – post 4, workshop preparation
 July – Workshop online
 August – Community guide is delivered
 September – video launch; datasets are published; layman's report is published on website and disseminate on social media

Plan efforts and resources

>> Minimum 1 post about the project on social media per month (= 7 posts)
 Post 1- March - Launch the project; partners id
 Post 2- April - 1st fisherwomen is trained/collects samples OR Earth day
 Post 3- May – anecdotal is collected; other women are trained
 Post 4 – June – Analysis of water samples in the lab; video footages
 Post 5- July – workshop with stakeholders
 Post 6 – August - Community guide finished and delivered to community
 Post 7 – September - end of the project; video
 Other possible posts to disseminate the project materials:

- Website page (May-June)
- Dataset on CoastNet (September)
- Layman's report (September)